

Foreign Educational Institutions in India: Is it a Matter of Concern?

Dr. Mohd. Talib Ather Ansari

MANUU, College of Teacher Education, Bidar Karnataka, India.

Email: talibmanuu@rediffmail.com

ABSTRACT

A good education is essential for gaining success in life. It has the ability to help individuals attain their greatest potential while also fostering a fair and inclusive society. As a result, the government has launched the National Education Policy 2020, which intends to establish a comprehensive framework for education. The goal of this research is to look at the many opportunities that foreign direct investment may give for educational settings in India. It also looks for aspects that may be utilized to enhance educational quality. The education system in India is forecast to develop substantially by 2030, with the role of educational privatization likely to rise dramatically. The purpose of this study, entitled " Foreign Educational Institutions in India: is it a matter of concern?" is to examine the numerous benefits, drawbacks, and implications of foreign direct investment in India's education sector.

Key words: *IB Curriculum, Edexcel Curriculum, NEP-2020, FEI Bill, Foreign Investment.*

1. Introduction

After a 34-year break, India's National Education Policy-2020 was approved and launched. It strives to enhance the country's educational system. It contains a variety of frameworks for elementary, secondary, and higher education. The policy comprises all professional, vocational, and technical teaching and training skill-based courses offered across India, and it suggests changing the school curriculum structure from 10+2 to 5+3+3+4.

Previously, board categories were just for the 10th and 12th grades; today, all courses and classes are essential. New structure of NEP-2020, allowed students to enter from age of 03 and continue for basic foundation courses and start pre-primary education for five years (03+2) primary education for next three years, lower secondary for next three years, and then combined secondary and higher secondary studies. All students can enrol in multiple streams like, science students can study arts subjects along with History, students may study Political Science and Chemistry. This is very valuable for both instructors and students, who may now self-evaluate their selves. This policy also includes many entry and exit doors for degree students, if a student decides to drop in the midst of a course, NEP allows it and the student may get a diploma, certificate, or degree for it, but it will cause issues for both the student and the professors. According to experts, this multiple entrance and departure option may boost dropout rates.

2. Foreign Education in India

Western educational systems are well-known for having a transformational influence on emerging countries. The relevance of Western education systems may be observed in the favourable effects they have on economic development. They are credited for hastening the growth of emerging countries and increasing the productivity of their population. Despite the multiple benefits of education, developing-country institutions sometimes

fail to address cultural and lifestyle contrasts between the Western world and the developing world, such as India. India remains a difficult market for foreign education, particularly for policymakers in the country. Since the 1990s, the government has been hesitant to accept foreign investors into its higher education industry, owing to a total absence of laws and the difficulties of the procedure.

The new National Educational Policy in education-2020 is intended to liberalize international university enrolment in India. It will provide them with specific exemptions from content and regulatory obligations. Many feel that India would have access to excellent education, while others fear that it would create inequality and overburden the existing school system. The plan has a lot of flaws, but it is also an excellent illustration of globalization, which is a complex process with worldwide trends.

The Western educational system is predicated on institutionalized, curriculum-based learning. This form of education often begins in elementary school and continues through college. In Western schools, instructors are often subject matter specialists, and classrooms resemble an indoor setting. Students are taught to interact with one another in a manner resembling that of a real-world society via a system of norms and regulations. In addition, Western schools emphasize the development of the abilities essential for a sophisticated industrial society to flourish. This is due to the fact that, in order to compete in the global market, students are expected to be aware of and competent in a variety of career-related skills.

3. Higher Education in India

India features one of the most comprehensive higher education systems in the world. However, its Gross Enrolment Ratio is just 27.1 per cent, which is much lower than countries such as Brazil and China. To attain pre-distinction, India must increase its foreign direct investment and expand its knowledge base. In addition to opening the door to foreign equity investments in the education sector, the government intends to increase private investment. Finance Minister Nirmala Sitharaman declared during her budget address that the government is dedicated to obtaining more foreign direct investment and inflows of cash to enhance the education system.

4. Structure of Indian Universities

- Central Universities

The MHRD Department of Higher Education is responsible of overseeing central universities' operations. Which are under the HRD ministry of India, and till 2021, there are 54 central universities in the country.

- State Universities.

The oldest known date when the universities of Madras, Calcutta, and Mumbai were established was in 1857. State universities are managed by the governments of various states and territories in India. As of 2021, the University Grants Commission has identified 441 state universities.

- Deemed Universities

The first institute get the status as “Deemed to be university” accorded to “The Indian Institute of Science” in May of 1958. As of November 30, 2021, the University Grants Commission has listed 126 institutes that have been granted deemed university status. The list is compiled by the Department of Education.

- Private Universities

Private universities but they are not authorised to award degrees and also are not permitted to operate off-campus facilities or open colleges with their affiliation. and are approved by UGC, as of November 2021 there are 397 private Universities are listed in UGC.

As of November 2021, there are 1018 universities in India. In states like Haryana, Delhi, Karnataka, Rajasthan, Puducherry, and Goa, there are different kinds of universities. With 85 universities, Rajasthan has the most of any state. It also has the most private schools, with 52. Tamil Nadu has the most universities, with 28 that are considered to be universities. West Bengal and Karnataka each have 34 state universities, and Delhi, which is the capital of India, has the most central universities in a state.

Some other universities in India can also give degrees, but they don't have to follow the same rules as the universities listed above. They are not called universities in a formal sense. Instead, they are called independent organizations.

5. Foreign Schools Already exist in India

Long-established foreign schools may be found all across India. These international schools in India adhere to the worldwide curriculum or a particular national curriculum, such as the International Baccalaureate, Edexcel, or Cambridge International Examinations. These institutions may also provide courses that vary from those typically provided in India. The particular curricula are as follows:

- **The International Baccalaureate Curriculum**

In 1968, the International Baccalaureate was founded. It provides numerous educational Courses tailored for students of varying ages, such as the International Baccalaureate Diploma Courses, the International Baccalaureate Career-related courses, and the Middle years International Baccalaureate Programme. The name "IB" may now apply to both the organization and its numerous programs.

- **Edexcel Curriculum**

Edexcel is a British education and examination board that was established in 1996. Sometimes referred to as Pearson Edexcel. It administers examinations based on the UK or British curriculum and delivers diplomas to schools worldwide.

- **Cambridge International Examinations**

In 1858, Cambridge Assessment was formed. It is mostly recognized for its school-leaving credentials. Universities in the United Kingdom, Canada, the United States, and elsewhere recognize Cambridge's credentials. It will unite with another university publishing in 2021 to become Cambridge University Press.

6. NEP-2020 and foreign investment in education in India

The premier education market in India is estimated to increase at a quick rate of 38 per cent through 2030, which is much more than the expected growth of the GDP, which is 2 per cent. With approximately 37.4 million students enrolled in higher education institutions, it is the world's largest talent provider. The Covid-19 epidemic has contributed to the growth of online education in India, and it has also presented the educational industry

with additional opportunity to enhance its services. In addition, the Indian government has unveiled the National Education Policy 2020, a comprehensive approach for the education system.

According to J. Knight; *“Internationalization at the national, sector, and institutional levels is defined as the process of integrating an international, intercultural, or global dimension into the purpose, functions or delivery of higher education.”*

The National Educational Policy-2020 aims to provide a flexible curriculum that will enable Students may choose dual mode education system a Major subject or course and a minor subject or course or programme of study simultaneously from any accessible stream of instruction. The NEP also establishes a framework for premier overseas institutions to enter India.

- India has the second largest higher education system in the world.
- One of the largest pools of manpower.
- Ranked as 72 among 132 countries in Global Talent Competitive Index (2020)
- Only 26% students enrolled for higher education in comparison to all people in that age group.
- NEP 2020 proposes to nearly double it to 50% by 2035.
- Before we massify the current education systems, let’s explore what internationalization could possibly do.

7. Foreign Universities in India

NIEPA conducted a study about the building of overseas campuses in India. Eight of the top 200 institutions in the world expressed interest in establishing a campus in India. The lenient regulatory environment in India might enhance the country's reputation as a viable destination for overseas students with some recommendation like

- NEP 2020 Proposes a Legislative Framework.
- FEI Bill.
- FEI as Foreign Educational Provider.
- India as global study destination.
- Collaboration with foreign higher educational institutions in academia and research like...

- (i) Twinning arrangements.
- (ii) Credit transfers.
- (iii) Alignment of the curriculum.
- (iv) Global citizenship approach.
- (v) Academic and research collaborations.

8. Challenges, Concern and Benefits Ahead

Despite the NEP-2020 and the Government of India's attempts to foster cooperation in numerous areas, significant obstacles remain for higher education institutions that want to establish a base of operations in India.

- The many rules and licenses necessary to operate educational institutions in India discourage many international educational institutions from the rest of the globe.
- The National Education Policy (NEP-2020) has been implemented slowly. Multiple clarifications are required to make it more universally compatible.
- Education at foreign colleges widens the divide between rural and urban India.
- Diverse ranking systems use distinct methodologies to select the nation's top institutions. This makes it difficult for international colleges of excellent quality to enter the top 100.
- The formation of a single governing body for higher education is a step in the right direction, but its operation and integration with other authorities must be explained.
- The plan to create a uniform testing body for higher education is a start in the right direction, but its operation and integration with other authorities must be specified.
- The problem of brain drain plaguing the Indian economy is a consequence of the growing number of Indians who prefer to pursue higher education abroad. To counteract this situation, the Government of India must foster an atmosphere that encourages the retention of Indian talent.

Benefits inclusion of Foreign Universities

- Exposure to international education
- Higher employability factors

- Increases confidence.
- Wider intellectual horizons.
- Upward productivity.
- Creation of holistic T-L envt.
- Devt in innovations and educational technology
- Cost effective degrees.

Specified Challenges ahead

- Problem of successful implementation of the proposed guidelines
- Academic autonomy to Foreign educational institutes.
- Problem of migration of teachers.
- Inclusion of students from diverse social and economic backgrounds.
- Migration of Indian students will not be prevented.
- Inhibiting factors behind cross border student flows.
- Leads to knowledge mismatch.

9. Conclusion And Suggestions

- 1) Higher education institutions have to re strategize in their bit to respond to internationalization.
- 2) With the increasing number of people in higher education, India may allow foreign universities to enter the market.
- 3) A proper regulatory framework is required.
- 4) Regulations should focus on quality assurance and accreditation.
- 5) There should be reorientation at national and institutional level on the purpose of education.
- 6) Institutions of learning have to reconsider their principal function as inculcators of right attitudes and values to the students.
- 7) Should endeavor to include character and good attitude, effective teaching as criteria.
- 8) The culture of the nation should be taken along with the western culture in the process of internationalization.

India may let foreign institutions to join the education market in order to provide enough infrastructure and improve capacities in light of the growing number of students in higher education. Allowing international institutions

to join the Indian market may be encouraged, but a robust regulatory framework is also essential to ensure that their operations are conducted securely and effectively. Due to the rapid development of higher education in a number of nations, the import-export dynamics of higher education have changed. Various frameworks and reports that can be used to improve the efficiency of foreign investment in education are advantageous, but due to the complexity of the higher education sector in India, the country's policymakers are currently working on developing regulations that will allow international universities to operate in the country; these regulations should emphasize quality assurance and accreditation. As anticipated, the NEP-2020 rollout will be gradual, and many of the obstacles will likely remain the same. One analyst said that it would be necessary to repatriate a percentage of the income to fund administrative costs, a concern shared by many. Another individual said that the use of the Indian campus will be a priority.

There is a need for branch campuses in India, but the perceived costs and dangers are prohibitive. India's government should give financial assistance to help defray these expenditures of higher education.

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